

IMPLICATION OF TEACHERS' BURNOUT TO TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Implication of Teachers' Burnout to Teaching Effectiveness: A Phenomenological Study

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Abstract

This study investigated the implication of teachers' burnout to teaching effectiveness. This study ascertained the experiences, realizations and insights of the teachers of Munoz and Boay Elementary School, Monkayo East District, Davao de Oro as they experienced burnout while they delivered teaching effectiveness toward the learners. In the course of the study, those experiences, realizations and insights of eight teachers were identified. Using qualitative phenomenological research design, analysis of data revealed that the teachers' burnout make teachers tired, stress, irritated, drained, exhausted and the contributing factor were heavy workload, overwork, urgent reports, pressure by school head and toxic colleague. The effect of teachers' burnout to teaching effectiveness were negative wherein it resulted on ineffective in teaching delivery, less work enthusiasm, less creativity and efficiency to deliver teaching performance. As a result, the teachers realized that the teaching effectiveness delivered for the sake of learners' despite of effect of burnout. Teachers, school head and higher authorities must continue to do their share to eliminate burnout and continue deliver the teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: *teachers' burnout, implication, teaching effectiveness, teachers, school head*

Introduction

Burnout describes as physical, emotional and psychological condition of teacher. It developed through stress, anxiety and depression in the workplace that produce feelings of exhaustion, cynicism and reduced personal accomplishment. Holt (2022) pointed out that teachers' burnout is a condition of work related stress and anxiety that affects physical, emotional and psychological aspect of teachers which resulted to productivity of teacher.

Campbell (2021) pointed out that teacher's burnout is critical problem prevalent in school. It is proved by Gerhenson (2022) that teachers' burnout developed thru heavy workload, overwork and pressure which contributes negative implication to teachers and to the effective teaching delivery. Furthermore, Mayo (2022) confirmed that stress, and depression reduces work motivation, energy and teaching competence of teacher. Scott (2022) added that anxiety reduces teaching performance and drops productivity of teachers.

It is the belief of schools of Monkayo that teaching is stressful one that need of suitable attention, care and proper support. And it is also a mandate to every school heads to create the learning environment conducive to teaching and learning in order to make it healthy for the teachers and learners and free from risk to achieve higher learning outcome (Republic Act 9155). However, there are reported teachers who need of medical attention and proper treatment due to prolonged stress and job burnout for too much paper works that being required to them and also being too busy for different school programs, projects and activities that they have performed in school.

However, the teacher burnout is perceived to have negative implication to the teaching effectiveness. The researcher has co-teacher that experienced of depression due to pressure in preparing paper works that has been assigned by the school head which lead him to loss of appetite in work. Subsequently, the researcher experienced also of burnout due to overwork in school for the teaching and non-teaching task in the preparation of the conduct of the monitoring and evaluation by the schools' division office that push me to physical and emotional breakdown which reduce my motivation to deliver effective teaching performance.

It is on the above context that the researcher wanted to examine the experiences of public elementary school teachers regarding their teaching effectiveness as affected by burnout. Thus the researcher wants to push through with this endeavor to investigate deeply and specifically the implication of teachers' burnout to teaching effectiveness.

Lastly, the researcher had seen the urgency of the study for the researchers have not come across with a study conducted in Monkayo.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the experiences of teachers' burnout and its implications to teaching effectiveness of the teachers. Research questions were the following:

1. What are the experiences of participants on burnout?
2. What are the implication of burnout to the participants' teaching effectiveness?
3. What are the insights gained by the participants from their experiences?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the qualitative phenomenological research design. Freeman, Preissle, Roulston and Pierre (2017) stressed that

qualitative research is a process of naturalistic inquiry that seeks an in-depth understanding of social phenomena within their natural setting. Kitchenham (2018) also illustrates that the phenomenology is a form of qualitative research which looks for in-depth at non-numerical data and uses interviews and observation notes in gathering relevant information from the identified participants.

Then, phenomenological form was appropriate design utilized of this study because the relevant experience including the deeper thoughts of the participants extracted efficiently. Jeynes (2015) confirmed that the relevance of the phenomenology is to gather appropriate insight from the experiences of the participants and to explore the deeper human thoughts, feelings and understanding to produce genuine results for the study.

Participants

The participants in this study were the classroom teachers of Boay Elementary School and Muñoz Elementary School, Monkayo East District who was in the service for 10 years or more. These teachers are having more knowledge and experience about the teachers' burnout and teaching effectiveness.

The researcher employed the purposive sampling technique in selecting the participants. Creswell (2015) noted that purposive sampling used and popular in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information rich cases to the phenomenon of interest. Thus, initially the researcher will be opted to come up with eight participants for the in-depth interview (IDI). They were identified through the pseudonyms for confidentiality purposes.

Considering the importance of privacy of the research participants, the researcher assigned pseudonyms to assure that their identity was protected.

Procedure

The study was presented to ethics committee for review to ensure that the guidelines on ethics was properly complied. After the ethics committee conducted the review a certification issued to the researcher to signify that the study ethical compliant and allowing the researcher to conduct this study.

After complying the ethical consideration, the researcher formulated interview guide that utilized to gather relevant information from the participants for the completion of the study with the help of her adviser.

After completion of the interview guide, it submitted to the panel of experts for validation. Indeed, their suggestion very necessary to make the interview guide scholarly and comprehensively. After the validation of the research instrument by the panel of experts, the researcher submitted a letter to the schools division superintendents and school principals to asked permission for the conduct of the in-depth interview (IDI) of the eight participants to gather the qualitative data.

After securing the permission from schools division superintendent and school principal the researcher started to conduct the in-depth interview to the identified participants.

As a matter of procedure, data collected through audio recording of interviews that took place in quite environment that make possible clear recording of voices. This audio recording of the interview of the eight participants were transcribed verbatim by the researcher. After the transcription and theme, it was presented to the participants for their confirmation.

Data Analysis

In the qualitative strand transcribing the participants' answers is essential since it is the basis for researcher's analysis. Then, a clear-spotting utilized in order to ensure that the recordings and the transcribed documents are relatively complete and accurate. In analyzing the data, the researcher administered thematic analysis. The thematic analysis was one of the most common forms of analysis in qualitative research. It emphasized pinpointing, examining and recording patterns (themes) within the data. Themes were patterns across data sets that important to the description of a phenomenon and were associated to a specific research question.

Information and data collected and identified cared and considered confidential. The security of it is not compromised. In the event that the study is published, the participants' identity withheld. The gathered data stored properly, archived securely and safely. Measures taken to protect anonymity and privacy of identity of every participant. Finally, after the study, the researcher disposed properly the survey questionnaires, audio tape and recorded data.

Ethical Considerations

Ethics involves being responsive to the rights of the participants and prioritizing respect for individuals required by the research. (Creswell, 2013) For ensuring the integrity, quality and transparency, this agreed standards of good research practices. The ethical standard in the conduct of the research and the protocol assessments carefully observed, the researches by properly securing the following;

Ethical aspects of the study were observed. The participants were given invitation and have fully informed about the objectives of the study; they are given freedom to participate or not. Further, this research infers that an individual has the right to freely decide to participate in a research study without fear of coercion and with a full knowledge of what is being investigated. Then, the fact that

participation is voluntary, participants can be withdrawn their statement anytime without a fear of penalty and fines.

Measures to protect the privacy and confidentiality of respondents strictly observed in the conduct of the study. They informed of their rights to ask clarifications, to interrupt, to criticize the way the questions are asked, to decline to answer some questions and to withdraw anytime from the study. Further the participants informed and assured that the data collected for this study only revealed the truthful result authentic and original and strictly used for academic purposes only, hence, mean no harm to any of them.

One of the foundations of research ethics was the idea of informed consent. Essentially, this means that potential research participants must be completely informed about procedures and risk implicated in research and must request their approval to participate. Simply put, informed consent means that participants should understand that they are partaking in research and what the research need of them without having coerced and deceived. Prior to conducting study, I choose participants' prospects and ask their permission to get involved in my study. The participants were given invitation and have fully informed about the objectives of the study; they were given freedom to participate or not. I make follow up through text and call to confirm their decision. I undergo all the processes advanced by Creswell (2015) as symbol of respect for the person involved in the study.

For this research, the appropriate identified recruiting parties were the teachers from public school, since the target participants are the teachers of their respective school. They are the ideal partners of the investigator achieve a well-established working relationship with the selected participants. Such partnership could have expected to provide greater awareness of the importance of this research study.

The researcher implied an intention of not harming and preventing harms occurring participants both physical and psychological nature. To uphold confidentiality, the research participants' names not used to identify comments, responses and works in the study. They were given pseudonyms for confidentiality purposes and backgrounds from the observation and backgrounds from the observation and information gathered by the researcher. I explained to the IDI participants' verbally and in writing the objectives of this research study and I asked them to sign a written consent. The informants also informed of the results and findings of the study as due recognition for their involvement. The participants had the right to refuse to answer the question that makes them comfortable.

This study is important for both school heads and teachers. The result helped to create school learning dynamics to produce efficient teachers and effective teaching delivery for the benefits of learners and school as a whole. The researcher made clear to the participants that they were not receive anything material and money in exchange for their involvement in the study as this might violate objectivity of data that collected in the process. Instead, general benefit comes in the form of awareness and information about the importance of ethics in the organization. Light snack served after the interview as token of respect and reciprocity.

The researcher does not have any conflict of interest since she is not part of the school nor related to the participants who are involved in the study. In addition, she was not trying to prove her claims with regards on teachers' burnout and its implication to teaching effectiveness of the teachers based on my personal experience but an interest in which helped to improve the program.

In the essence that the falsehood about the author's identity and the nature and true purpose of the study should be avoided, this research most relevant in experimentation where personal knowledge of the purposes might change people's behavior hence this is not applicable for this study.

Notably, the researcher ensures to get a written permission from the office of the schools division superintendents and school principals to conduct study within the school. After which, the researcher was begun conducting and in-depth interview for this qualitative study.

As can be seen, the author of this research is the one whose name appeared in the title page of this manuscript. She is the author of this research because she makes substantial contributions to conception and design or acquisition of data or analysis and interpretation of data; drafting the article or revised it critically for important intellectual content and responsible for the final approval version to be published. Moreover, the author of this research manuscript contributed mentally and spiritually to the scientific content molds the research aspect in presentable and understandable form.

Results and Discussion

Eight permanent teachers, ten years in the service and above in the served as study participants. They were purposely chosen for the in-depth interview. They were the sources of pieces of information and data for the phenomenon under study.

Since this study required a thorough investigation and in compliance with reliability and transferability concern in qualitative studies, the research employed the qualitative phenomenological research design. In doing so, the researcher would be able to undergo in-depth interview through one-on-one interview with the research participants to gathered necessary data for analysis, code and thematic.

The structured themes and the emerging therein were made as bases in broadening the discussion of the findings in this study. Each theme was linked and supported with related literature and studies.

Burnout While Performing Teaching Duty. The experienced of the research participants on teachers' burnout were tired and loses motivation, stress due to heavy workload, easily irritated, drained and exhausted and no energy to perform. The findings manifested that during burnout teachers felt of negative feelings such as tired, drained and irritable behavior. And it lost energy to perform the teaching duty.

The finding parallel to the statement of Movchan (2022) that teachers during burnout have felt depressed, fatigue and exhaustion which losing their passion about their job.

It is also consonance to the articulation of Walker (2023) that when teacher in burnout they felt of being tired due to stress which make them struggle even to perform even simple task in school.

It is further conversed by Parks (2017) that during burnout contributes too much stress to teacher lead them to more irritable behavior that affect the teaching and learning delivery.

Factors Contribute of the Burnout of Teachers. The theme generated from the research participants were heavy workload, overwork, urgent reports and pressure by the school head. The finding revealed that heavy workload, being overwork in school, submission of urgent reports and pressure of the school head to teacher factors contributed teachers' burnout.

The finding confirms the declaration of Campbell (2021) that burnout develop due to excessive workload that being apportioned to teachers, overwork to perform different assign task and pressure by the school head factors of burnout of teachers.

It is also parallel to the statement of Omodan (2016) that too much paper reports required the teachers to do so and submission of reports that always urgently required is another factor of burnout.

It is further conversed by Gupta and Goel (2016) that lack of necessary supports and attention of colleague and pressure contributed by the school administration toward the teachers adds the burnout.

Managing of the Burnout. The research participants' responses produced the themes ask help from co-teachers, care to own self, remain in strength, sharing stressful experienced with family, support from family and remembering teaching a noble calling. The finding disclosed that teachers managed the burnout by capacitating of themselves through caring of self, remain in strength and remembering teaching a noble calling. Then, teachers gain courage from supports of the family and co-teachers.

The finding is in compliance with the articulation of Wooll (2022) that the support of family, co-teacher, school authorities and other is very important in eliminating the stress and depression of the teacher.

And it is added by Firestone (2022) that during stress and burnout teacher needs of the support from the family and co-worker to sustain their strength that requires to the efficient delivery of service toward the learners.

However, it is further converse by Hess (2020) that teachers managed burnout by caring of themselves teacher through eating nutritious food and get enough sleep.

Support Extended by Family. The themes generated were help and encouraged to do job, moral support, showing comfort during burnout, give emotional support and helping in household chores. The finding revealed that during burnout the family extended their support to teachers to make them effectively deliver their teaching performance in school for the welfare of the learners.

The finding confirms the statement of Movchan (2023) that during burnout teacher needs of the support from their family. Moral supports extended by family become their strength so that they continue to deliver efficient service toward the learners.

This is consonance with the statement of Firestone (2022) that during burnout teacher needs of care and moral support of the family. The care and support of the family source of strength of teachers that encouraged them to do their teaching task for the efficient delivery of service toward the learners.

This is further parallel to the statement of Wooll (2022) that supports of the family very important factors that eliminates the stress and anxiety of teachers for better delivery of teaching service.

Support Extended by Colleague. The emerging themes were working as a team, support mechanism, source of strength, advices, motivation and encouragement, source of knowledge and helping one another. The finding disclosed that the colleague extended supports to teachers to make them productive in their teaching performance for the welfare of the learners. As a team in school they were helping one another and colleague serves as source of strength and motivation and knowledge because of their advices, encouragement and knowledge shared to each members.

The finding confirms to the statement of Hawthorne (2022) noted that teaching effectiveness is the result of an effort of the teachers who are provided of proper care and support from their colleague within the healthy learning environment.

This is consonance with the statement of Firestone (2022) that during burnout teacher needs of support of the colleague. The supports of the colleague give encouragement to teacher to deliver effective toward the learners.

This is further parallel to the statement of Finch (2023) that the co-teacher serves as supports system that need of teacher to make the work lighter and to makes the delivery of teaching performance toward the learners efficient and effective.

Support Extended by School Administration. The emerging themes were lead to deliver effective instruction, guides and encouraged, always extended support, conduct school-based training, always guides and motivates, provide classroom supplies, sincere to guide

and never experienced being supported. The finding disclosed that the school head extended support to teachers during burnout to make them effective and efficient to deliver the teaching performance toward the learners through giving appropriate instruction, guidance and motivation to perform well, in service training to equip with teaching skills and classroom supplies necessary for effective delivery of service.

The finding is parallel to the statement of Hawthorne (2022) noted that teaching effectiveness is the result of an effort of the teachers who are provided of proper care and support from school administration within the healthy learning environment.

The finding supported by Bordia (2022) in her testimony that teachers need of supports from school principal especially in hard times of their career due to stress, anxiety and depression to remain effective to perform their teaching task for achieving higher learning outcome.

This is further supported by Conyers (2016) in his articulation that school authorities focused to equip teachers with necessary skills through conduct of in-service training and provided with supplies that needed to effectively deliver teaching performance.

Implication of Burnout to Deliver of Teaching Effectiveness. The emerging themes were ineffective in teaching, less enthusiasm, creativity and efficient, makes the day dark and cloudy and no effort to teach. The finding revealed that burnout had negative impact to teachers and to their performance in teaching which directly affects the learning of learners. Burnout reduces enthusiasm, creativity and efficiency in teaching. It makes the day of teachers' dark and cloudy that loses effort to perform teaching duty which lead ineffective performance.

The finding parallel to the declaration of Bozkus (2023) that burnout has negative impact to teacher efficacy, teacher enthusiasm and job satisfaction. It is also affects the classes, school climate and school culture.

The finding confirmed by Lynch (2016) that burnout has negative influence to teaching competence, skills and ability of teacher which directly affects delivery of the effective teaching and learning toward the learners.

It is further confirmed by the articulation of Overton (2023) that when the teachers suffer from burnout, their productivity drops and they become less innovative and more likely to make errors which the delivery of instruction, classroom management and students' discipline are affected.

Strategy Employ to Deliver Teaching Effectiveness. The emerging themes were positive outlook in life, technology integration, utilize a diverse activity, knowing pupil, inspire and be sensitive to pupils' need, utilize technology, plan lesson efficiently and employs variety teaching methods. The finding revealed that strategies to deliver teaching effectiveness starts from teachers. They need to make themselves composed through looking positive side of life. Then followed by pupils through recognizing their strength and weaknesses basis for lesson preparation. Lastly, the application of technology and variety of teaching methodologies.

This finding agreed with the statement of Brower (2022) it is the obligation of the effective teacher to equip himself always and be available and employs appropriate teaching strategies to deliver the curriculum for the development of the learners in different level.

The finding confirmed by Miller (2021) that teaching delivery become effective the teacher need to reduce exposing themselves to job stressor and emotional toxic and focus to develop the learners through utilizing technology in a variety of teaching strategies.

The finding further confirmed by the pronouncement of Valcour (2016) that during burnout teachers should shifted their perspective into happy and positive side of life and focus to the need of the pupils.

Observation on the Implication of Burnout to the Teaching Effectiveness. The emerging theme were affected learning due to absenteeism, cannot focus teaching effectively may affect the learners, may feel less satisfaction, reduces energy, passion and sense of accomplishment and emotional exhaustion and cynicism. The finding revealed that the burnout has negative implication to teachers and to their teaching performance that affects the learners. Burnout produces feelings of emotional exhaustion and cynicism that reduces satisfaction, energy, passion and sense of accomplishment of teachers. It also loses focus on teaching that lead to absenteeism of teachers that affect greatly their performance.

The finding is in agreement of the presentation of Lynch (2016) that teachers' burnout has a negative impact to the competence, skills and ability of teachers that affect the delivery of the effective teaching and learning toward the learners.

The is parallel to the articulation by Provenzano (2018) that burnout reduce motivation and performance of teachers that significantly affect the teaching and learning process.

This is parallel further by the statement of Forastieri (2016) that burnout associated with worse academic achievement and lower the quality of teaching and learning delivery.

Learning from Experiences of the Participants. The emerging themes were necessary to be strong, need to take a rest, eat and sleep, renew strength, need to manage burnout well, must be resilient enough, must know coping up stress accordingly and remembering passion and finding joy in teaching. The finding disclosed that teachers overcome the burnout through physical, psychological and mental preparation to regain strength for effective delivery of teaching duties to the learners. In physical, teacher takes a necessary rest

and sleep and eat nutritious food to renew strength. Then, for psychological, the teacher improves his strong emotion by remembering his teaching commitment. Finally, for mental, the teacher develops the ability to cope up the stress and ability to become resilient in order to manage the burnout well.

This finding parallel to the statement of Lyness (2022) that during stress and anxiety teachers necessary to manage so that the effect could not be fatal. Thus, it is necessary to eat nutritious and get enough sleep to regain the strength for effective delivery of teaching performance.

The finding supported by Hess (2020) in her articulation that during burnout, it is necessary for teachers to take a break from work, having a rest, sleep and eat nutritious food to regain strength that essential for the delivery of effective teaching strategies for the learners.

The finding further supported by Felson (2023) that during burnout, it is very necessary for teacher to prepare his both physical and psychological aspect through exercise, enough sleep, eating nutritious food and recall the commitment to teaching.

Improve Effective Teaching Delivery. The emerging theme were knowing learners' level and capacity, use relevant teaching materials, deliver new learning, learn to adopt situation, be more motivated to work, implementing technology in teaching method, efficiently organizing and handling workload, looking at the brighter side of life and focus delivering lesson. The finding revealed that teachers improves teaching delivery through making himself composed and prepared to perform his teaching duties. Conduct assessment to determine the level of ability of the learners to address the weaknesses. And utilization of relevant learning materials and application of appropriate teaching methodologies.

The finding is in agreement of the presentation of Cox (2015) that effective teaching is combination of skills and abilities of teachers performed in the classroom, active engagement of the students and the application of an appropriate teaching instruction and strategies. These works together to produce quality results.

The finding consonance to the articulation of Chong (2021) that teacher need to be physically and psychologically ready and equip himself with necessary knowledge and skills to deliver effectively the teaching and learning for the learners.

Further, finding confirmed by the declaration of Hawthorne (2022) that effective teaching delivery teachers should implement the appropriate teaching strategy that suit to the learning ability of the learners.

Advice given to co-teacher ways to make learning environment healthy. The emerging theme were helping and understanding each other, do not bring personal problem to workplace, just go with the flow, be collaborative, attended trainings to improve teaching skills, do job with happy heart learn and apply new things, cooperate and collaborate and always put love to profession. The finding disclosed that teachers performs their duties happily.

Their personal problem leaves at home. They understand, helps and collaborate each other to achieve their goals. And they attended trainings and seminar to improve teaching skills for better delivery of service.

The finding confirmed the statement of Mintz (2022) that in the healthy school environment teachers are working together happily who collaborate each other with the support of the school head in order to achieve the goals of the school.

The finding parallel to the statement of Parks (2017) that the healthy learning environment is product of collaboration of proactive teachers who understand and help each other in order to achieve the goals of the school.

Moreover, the finding is in similar with the declaration of Movchan (2022) that healthy learning environment teachers are collaborating and helping each other focus to achieve one common goal.

Advice given to school administration ways to make learning environment healthy. The emerging theme were equipping teachers with necessary knowledge and skills, provide regular break, for teachers, conduct training focusing stress management, distribute loading fairly and reduced paper works, and be sensitive to teachers feeling and sentiment. The finding disclosed that the teachers expects from school administration to equip them with necessary knowledge and skills in teaching and stress management through training, provided with regular break to regain the strength, reduced paper works, distribute the loading fairly and sensitive to the feelings and sentiments of teachers.

The finding parallel to the statement of Lucas (2022) that the expectation of teachers towards the school head are leader with the heart, sensitive to their needs and listen to their problems. A leader possesses of intellect capability that capable to equip teachers with knowledge and skills through coaching, mentoring and even to facilitates training.

The finding parallel to the articulation of Krulder (2023) that the teachers need the support of school head to equip their capabilities to deliver teaching task and supported them to achieve their best for the school and for the learners.

Moreover, the finding is in similar with the declaration of Balow (2023) that the support of school administrator needed to extend to the teachers in order to overcome the burnout and to make them active to perform their function is to train them how to manage the stress and to become more resilient.

Advice given to higher authorities' ways to make learning environment healthy. The emerging theme were remove administrative task, increased teachers' salary, allocating textbooks in school, reduce teaching loads and stable program for teachers and learners. The finding manifested that desire of teachers to uplift teaching condition through removing administrative task, assigned to teachers, reduce teaching loads, allocating textbooks for better delivery of lesson to learners and establish stable program for teachers and learners. Further, it is the desire of teachers to uplift their living condition through increase of salary.

The finding is in agreement of the articulation of Basas (2022) that the petition of teachers to DepEd is to establish teaching condition by removing the additional non-teaching task assign to teachers which make them overwork and living condition through increase of salary and other benefits.

The finding supported the pronouncement of Weeks (2023) that common causes of teachers' burnout in school those additional administrative assignment. To reduce their burnout and make them effective to their work, higher authorities should remove additional work and continue value their effort for the school to achieve their best for the school and for the learners.

Moreover, the finding is in similar with the declaration of Malipot (2020) that the teachers busy performed administrative task which not related to teaching. To make them fruitful and productive higher authorities should remove administrative task and uplift their living condition for increasing their salary.

Implications for Practice

Based on the findings, the following implications for practice are offered.

On Burnout While Performing Teaching Duty. As noted in the finding of the study, burnout produced negative effect to teachers while they perform their teaching duty in school. It makes teachers tired, drained and produced irritable behavior. And it lost their motivation and energy to work due to stress and exhaustion.

On Factors Contribute of the Burnout of Teachers. The finding revealed that heavy workload, being overwork in school, submission of urgent reports and pressure of the school head to teacher factor contributed to teachers' burnout.

On Managing of the Burnout. As revealed in the findings of the study, the teachers managed the burnout by capacitating themselves through caring of self, remain in strength and remembering their commitment to teaching as a noble calling.

On Support Extended by Family. The finding presents that during burnout the family of teachers extended their support to teachers to make them effectively deliver their teaching performance in school for the welfare of the learners.

On Support Extended by Colleague. The findings disclosed that the colleague extended supports to teachers to make them productive in their teaching performance for the welfare of the learners. As a team in school they were helping one another and colleague serves as source of strength, motivation and knowledge because of their advices, encouragement and knowledge shared to each member.

On Support Extended by School Administration. The findings disclosed that the school head extended supports to teachers during burnout to make them effective and efficient to deliver the teaching performance toward learners through giving them appropriate instruction, guidance and motivation to perform well. The school conducts in-service training to equip teachers with teaching skills for effective delivery of teaching performance. In addition, classroom supplies afforded for effective delivery of service.

However, other finding confirms that some of the school heads failed to performed their function to support the teachers to perform their teaching duties productively. They failed to guide, motivate and encourage teachers to perform well, instead let them to work of their own to achieve the goal of the school.

On Influence of Burnout to Deliver of Teaching Effectiveness. As to influence of teachers' burnout had negative effect to teachers and to their performance in teaching which directly affects the learners. Burnout reduces enthusiasm, creativity and efficiency in teaching. It makes the day of teachers' dark and cloudy that loses effort to perform teaching duty which lead ineffective performance.

On Strategy to Employ to Deliver Teaching Effectiveness. The finding of the study shows; the strategies to deliver teaching effectiveness starts from teachers. They need to make themselves composed through looking positive side of life. Then followed by pupils through recognizing their strength and weaknesses basis for lesson preparation. Lastly, the application of technology and variety of teaching methodologies.

On Implication of Burnout to the Teaching Effectiveness. It is noted in the finding of the study, the burnout has negative implication to teachers and to their teaching performance that affects the learners. Burnout produces feelings of emotional exhaustion and cynicism that reduces satisfaction, energy, passion and sense of accomplishment of teachers. It also loses focus on teaching that lead to absenteeism of teachers that affect greatly their performance.

On Learning from Experiences of the Participants. The finding of the study revealed, the teachers overcome burnout through physical, mental and psychological preparation to regain strength for effective delivery of teaching duties to the learners. In physical, teacher takes a necessary rest, sleep and eat nutritious food to renew strength. Then, for psychological, the teacher improves his emotions by

remembering his commitment to teaching. Finally, for mental, the teacher develops ability to cope up the stress and develop ability to become resilient in order to manage the burnout effectively.

On Improves Effective Teaching Delivery. The finding disclosed that teachers improves teaching delivery through making himself composed and prepared to perform his teaching duties. Conduct assessment to determine the level of ability of the learners to address the weaknesses. And utilization of relevant learning materials and application of appropriate teaching methodologies.

On Advice Given to School Co-Teacher Ways to Make Learning Environment Healthy. The finding disclosed that teachers performs their duties happily. Their personal problem leaves at home. They understand, helps and collaborate each other to achieve their goals. And they attended trainings and seminar to improve teaching skills for better delivery of service.

On Advice Given to School Administration Ways to Make Learning Environment Healthy. The finding disclosed that teachers expects from school administration to equip them with necessary skills in teaching and knowledge on stress management through training. Provided with regular breaks to regain the strength. Reduced paper works and distributes the loading and become sensitive to the feelings and sentiment of teachers.

On Advice Given to Higher Authorities Ways to Make Learning Environment Healthy. The finding manifested that desire of teachers to uplift teaching condition through removing administrative task, assigned to teachers, reduce teaching loads, allocating textbooks for better delivery of lesson to learners and establish stable program for teachers and learners. Further, it is the desire of teachers to uplift their living condition through increase of salary.

Implications for Future Research

In as much as the study was limited to the responses of the teachers in Boay Elementary School and Muñoz Elementary School, Monkayo East District, Division of Davao de Oro, the following implications for future research are considered:

First, future research may be conducted by selecting other groups of teachers coming from the same school. Second, another research of the same focus may be conducted to another location to investigate the same phenomenon on understanding child protection policy. Third, conduct a re-interview of the same research participants and informants to see whether their understanding about teachers' burnout has changed over a period of time.

Finally, this study was conducted in a public elementary school; this investigation for the same phenomenon could be also conducted to among private schools. On other hand, the findings of the study are viewed from lens of the selected teachers' participants and informants. Another research could be conducted to find out the understanding of teachers' burnout among teachers of Munoz and Boay Elementary School.

Conclusions

The Implication of teachers' burnout to teaching effectiveness is the focus of the investigation. It is manifested clearly that burnout had negative effect to teachers and to teaching effectiveness that affects the learner, it is the bases of the higher authorities of DepEd to review the loading distribution, totally remove administrative task to teachers and provides the need of the school to make teachers productive and effectively deliver their teaching task for the welfare of the learners.

On the other hand, since the support of the school heads source of commitment of the teachers to make the teaching delivery effective, the school head shall equip teachers with knowledge and skills through conducting school-based training, avoid pressure to teachers and religiously perform their duties to create learning environment free from burnout such to make the teachers continually delivered their teaching duties productively.

Finally, since co-teachers source of strength and courage of teachers in the school in order to effectively perform their teaching duties, they need to work collaboratively as a team. They need to be cooperative and supportive to need of other by avoiding being toxic in the workplace.

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